

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: Nextflow on HPC
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	18-19 November 2025
Time of event	1-4:30pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>Outgrown your laptop? Learn how to take your bioinformatics pipelines to the next level by scaling them on Australia's national high performance computing (HPC) clusters.</p> <p>In collaboration with the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) and the Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre, this hands-on workshop will equip you with the practical skills to run and optimise efficient Nextflow workflows on HPC systems.</p> <p>Attendees will be guided through a series of hands-on exercises to configure nf-core workflows on NCI Gadi (PBS) and Pawsey Setonix (SLURM), and will iteratively develop a bioinformatics workflow to process larger files, and more samples.</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom over two three and a half hour sessions.</p> <p>The trainers led the sessions by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in the analysis. Participants then moved into breakout rooms where they had the chance to apply these skills with support from facilitators.</p> <p>The workshop followed the tutorial linked in the Training Materials section.</p> <p>A breakdown of timings and topics is provided in the schedule.</p> <p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p> <p>Number of participants = 33</p>
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/nextflow-hpc-workshop-2025
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945

	Workflow http://edamontology.org/data_2972
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	<p>This workshop is for Australian researchers and technical users (bioinformaticians, life scientists, and data scientists) who:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have access to HPC systems (e.g., institutional, national, or cloud-based clusters) • Have run simple Nextflow pipelines, typically in a one-sample-per-run or manual scripting context • Are now looking to scale up their workflows, optimise performance, and apply best practices for HPC environments <p>You must be associated with an Australian organisation for your application to be considered. Please note that participants will be supported with access to Gadi and Setonix computing resources for the duration of this workshop.</p>
Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completed the “Hello Nextflow” workshop, or have equivalent experience (e.g. basic understanding of how to create and run a Nextflow pipeline) • Basic command line skills, such as manipulating files and running scripts and tools • Familiarity with concepts like multi-sample processing and reproducible analysis (e.g. containers) • Familiarity with how HPC clusters work (e.g., job submission, compute nodes) • Requirement for scalable analysis, running Nextflow on HPCs and schedulers
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A shared Google Doc was used to facilitate discussions. • Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. • Participants were provided with access to training accounts running on Setonix and Gadi infrastructure.
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of the workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the differences between traditional HPC job submission (e.g.sbatch, qsub) and workflow execution via Nextflow (e.g. how main jobs and child tasks map to HPC job schedulers) • Configure and execute scalable Nextflow workflows on HPC systems, selecting appropriate queues, nodes and job resources (CPU, memory, walltime) for large-scale parallel tasks • Manage software environments for reproducible workflows using tools like singularity, and adapt these to fit within different HPC ecosystem constraints • Monitor and troubleshoot Nextflow workflows on HPC systems, identifying and resolving errors related to configuration, resource allocation and environment setup

Lead Trainers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Michael Geaghan, Senior Bioinformatician (Australian BioCommons), Sydney Informatics Hub (SIH), University of Sydney. • Fred Jaya, Senior Bioinformatician (Australian BioCommons), Sydney Informatics Hub (SIH), University of Sydney.
Facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Mitchell O'Brien, Sydney Informatics Hub (SIH), University of Sydney • Dr Georgina Samaha, Sydney Informatics Hub (SIH), University of Sydney • Dr Cali Willet, Sydney Informatics Hub (SIH), University of Sydney • Dr Kisaru Liyanage, National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) Australia • Wenjing Xue, National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) Australia • Dr Kristina Gagalova, Curtin University (Nextflow Ambassador) • Gayatri Aniruddha, The University of Western Australia • Dr Sarah Beecroft, Pawset (Technical Support) • Dr Abdullah Shaikh, National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) (Technical Support)
Training materials	https://sydney-informatics-hub.github.io/nextflow-hpc-workshop/
Related work	